

**CULTURE-BASED INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS IN ARLING PANLIPUNAN – 8
IN THE DISTRICTS OF ATIMONAN, SCHOOLS DIVISION OF QUEZON:
BASIS FOR STRENGTHENING THE LOCALIZATION AND
INDIGENIZATION OF INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS**

Karen Dayag Breganza ¹, Rex Emmanuel L. Asuncion, Ed.D. ²

*¹ Department of Education, Malinao Ilaya Integrated National High School
Atimonan, Quezon*

*² Marinduque State College, Graduate School Extension of Graduate Programs to
Quezonian Educational College, Inc. Atimonan, Quezon*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10902943>

ABSTRACT

The study focused on secondary school teachers of Araling Panlipunan 8 from the Atimonan Districts, utilizing purposive sampling to determine the availability and integration of culture-based instructional materials. To assess the availability, the study employed frequency and percentage, while the mean was used to identify gaps in the inventory of available culture-based instructional materials. The findings of this study provide several insights. First, concerning the availability of culture-based instructional materials, traditional materials such as lesson plans were reported to have a 68.75% availability among respondents. However, supplemental reading materials remained insufficient for most teachers. Second, within the category of Graphics and Interactives, physical objects were relatively well supplied, accounting for 43.75% of the available culture-based instructional materials, and dimension of culture elements, particularly values (75%) and language (75%), were highly accessible, reflecting their significant role within the cultural context. Regarding the integration of culture-based instructional materials, traditional materials demonstrated the highest level of culture-based integration, with eight respondents emphasizing tools and technology. Graphics and interactives also effectively integrated in the available culture-based instructional materials, as noted by nine respondents, focusing on tools and technology. Dimension of culture elements, such as clothing, were similarly well-integrated. Furthermore, the study identified notable gaps in the inventory of available culture-based instructional materials, with an overall mean score of 3.052, falling within the 'Agree' range. In conclusion, these

findings indicate that such materials are generally lacking in the surveyed population. Based on these findings, several recommendations are suggested.

Keywords: *Culture-based, Instructional, Materials, Araling Panlipunan, Inventory, Availability, Traditional materials*

INTRODUCTION

Education is key to preparing individuals to contribute to a country's development. Integrating into education and inculcating values, norms, practices, and traditions among students is necessary to preserve a nation's culture. This helps promote good character among the students. A powerful nationalistic spirit may be ingrained in pupils by teaching them the virtues of their local culture. Before teaching-learning, instructional materials should be created with activities that impart local cultural values (Susanti et al., 2021). In culture-based education, culture serves as the cornerstone of the government, sustainable development, and education. Culture is the lens through which abilities, skills, and information about a person and the world are shared. It also provides a technique, guiding principles, assessment, framework, and evaluation. It is a teaching method and educational concept in which the community's distinctive values, norms, cultural beliefs, knowledge, practices, legacy, language, and experiences serve as the foundation for students' learning. Incorporating cultural elements into education may lead to a fresh taste that might increase students' interest in the subject. Additionally, this may help students establish a solid link between what they learn in school and how they live. They could also promote a sense of nationalism and patriotism, and a strong sense of community connection. This will result in a positive shift in the country (Knowledge Review, n.d.).

With the dawn of information technology, most of the current contents of learning materials are often highly modernized and trendy, leading to a loss of interest by most students in culturally related content. This causes the deterioration of cultural appreciation by the new generation. Whether teaching elementary or high school students, it is more crucial than ever for instructors to include culturally responsive instruction in the classroom in an increasingly varied and multicultural society. Moreover, the variety among students is growing not only in terms of color and ethnicity but also in terms of economic level, sexual orientation, gender identity, and linguistic background. All students benefited from promoting inclusiveness, raising awareness of intercultural education, and approaching instruction with cultural sensitivity. Increasing intercultural understanding and inclusion promotes acceptance and helps children flourish in a world with increasing diversity, but also helps students with varied origins and needs to be achieved. Cultural awareness may be promoted in the classroom; however, there is also a need to ensure that the lesson plan considers diversity. Alternatively, include cross-cultural allusions and comparisons in the courses and homework to encourage personal connections among students of various origins. Including speakers from different backgrounds is an approach for giving a range of perspectives and real-world contexts to various topics. Depending on the culture in the classroom and the subject being taught, various methods may

promote cultural awareness and diversity in the lesson plan. Regardless of the subject, it would be best to try to relate teaching to current events (Drexel University School of Education, 2000). In doing so, teachers are compelled to use learning materials or even develop one that incorporates these values, beliefs, traditions, and norms as they help students become empathetic, obtain a better grasp of lessons and people, be more open-minded, feel more confident and safer, and be prepared to work in a diverse workspace.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the available culture-based instructional materials in Araling Panlipunan 8 in the Districts of Atimonan, Division of Quezon as basis for strengthening the localization and indigenization of instructional materials.

Specifically, this study sought answers to the following subproblems:

1. What are the available culture – based instructional materials in Araling Panlipunan 8 in the Districts of Atimonan, Division of Quezon, in terms of:
 - 1.1 Traditional materials;
 - 1.2 Graphics and interactives; and
 - 1.3 Dimension of culture?
2. What culture were integrated in the following available culture-based instructional materials in terms of:
 - 2.1 Traditional materials;
 - 2.2 Graphics and interactives; and
 - 2.3 Dimension of culture?
3. What gaps were noted in the inventory of available culture-based instructional materials?
4. What interventions could be proposed to strengthen the localization and indigenization of Culture-based instructional materials?

METHODOLOGY

This research aimed to assess the available culture-based instructional materials among Public Secondary Schools, Districts of Atimonan, Schools Division of Quezon, for the School Year 2022-2023. The respondents in this study were the 16 teachers in Araling Panlipunan 8 in Public Schools in the Districts of Atimonan, Quezon.

The research design was descriptive, which required quantitative methods to determine the available culture-based instructional materials.

The data collection locations for this study were the Secondary Public Schools, Districts of Atimonan, Schools Division of Quezon. The study was conducted throughout the School Year 2022 – 2023. It examined Araling Panlipunan 8 culture-based instructional materials, such as textbooks, lesson plans, workbooks, flashcards, supplemental reading materials, graphics, interactive materials, and dimensions of culture.

The Philippines was the locale of the study shown in Figure 3. Specifically, selected Secondary Schools under the Districts of Atimonan in the Division of Quezon are shown in Figure 3. The Atimonan Districts consists of public secondary schools; Atimonan National Comprehensive High School, Balubad National High School, Caridad National High School, Malusak National High School, San Rafael National High School, and Villa Ibaba National High School are from District I. While Maligaya Integrated National High School and Malinao Ilaya Integrated National High School are from District II. The researcher had selected Atimonan, Quezon as the focus of the study, to have the opportunity to make a positive impact on the local educational community. Enlightening people in Atimonan, Quezon about the benefits of using culture-based instructional materials can lead to a more culturally responsive and enriching educational experience for both teachers and students.

This research is based on Culatta's (2016), personalized learning initiative is a model focused on the development of a culture-based instructional material (IM). According to Culatta (2016), utilizing technology in the classroom should go beyond simply transferring print materials into a digital format, such as in reading. This approach does not foster innovative learning. The essence of the Personalized Learning Initiative lies in students using technology to enhance their problem-solving skills and accumulate experiences. It emphasizes that learning occurs when students leverage technology and experiences, known as the Personalized Learning Initiative.

While technology and experience aid in skill acquisition, learning itself is not the ultimate goal. The accumulation of experiences enables students to connect with themselves through their environment, emphasizing the role of culture in the learning process. A theory aligned with Culatta's model is the Functional Context Theory proposed by Sticht (2000). According to this theory, adult learners should possess a thorough understanding of their own culture, drawing on prior and relevant knowledge for more meaningful learning experiences. Embedding culture in a reading text for instructional purposes becomes crucial. This approach ensures that students receive input related to their own culture while simultaneously integrating culture into the context of learning specific language skills.

Research Population and Sample

Atimonan District	Name of Secondary Schools in Atimonan, Quezon	Number of Teachers in Araling Panlipunan 8
1	1. Atimonan National Comprehensive High School	2
1	2. Balubad Integrated National High School	2
1	3. Caridad Ilaya Integrated School	2
1	4. Malusak Integrated National High School	2
1	5. San Rafael National High School	1
1	6. Villa Ibaba Integrated National High School	1
2	7. Maligaya Integrated National High School	2
2	8. Malinao Integrated National High School	4
Total		16

Research Instrument

The self-made survey questionnaire underwent testing for validity and reliability with the assistance of a master teacher, school heads, and research experts. It was administered to ten (10) non-respondents and subsequently tested using Cronbach Alpha. The results were then reported to the research adviser and statistician for further actions.

The data were gathered, organized, and analyzed until a significant conclusion was reached. To facilitate data accumulation and simplify the presentation of statistical figures, the questionnaire was divided into three parts.

Part I focused on the available culture-based instructional materials in Araling Panlipunan 8, including traditional materials, Graphics and Interactive materials, and dimension of culture.

Part II delved into the integration of culture in the available culture-based instructional materials in Araling Panlipunan 8, covering traditional materials, Graphics and Interactive materials, and dimensions of cultures.

Part III address the gaps noted in the available inventory of culture-based instructional materials.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher developed the questionnaire based on the sub-problems identified in the preceding chapter. An expert team reviewed and aligned the survey questionnaire's content after its submission. The research questionnaire considered and incorporated the advice and commentary of these experts. It was then given to specialists who assessed the study questionnaire after considering all comments and suggestions. After obtaining

the experts' permission, the self-developed research questionnaire underwent an evaluation for validity and reliability. Before subjecting it to the Cronbach Alpha test, it was administered to ten (10) non-respondents. The statistician received a report of the findings and, if necessary, took further action. The researcher scrutinized whether traditional culture-based instructional materials in Araling Panlipunan 8 were present, as they were the subject of this research.

Furthermore, the researcher sent a letter of request to the Schools Division Superintendents of the eight (8) schools listed in Table 1. The data gathered from the eight secondary public schools were tallied, treated, analyzed, and interpreted according to the problems addressed in this research study. The researcher also reviewed available culture-based instructional materials in Araling Panlipunan 8 to determine the presence of culture-based instructional materials in terms of traditional materials such as textbooks, lesson plans, workbooks, flashcards, and supplemental reading materials. The second objective was to identify graphics and interactive materials, including physical objects, photographs, maps, multimedia, and games. The last objective was to determine the dimensions of culture, encompassing beliefs, norms and customs, symbols and language, social structures, material culture, cultural practices and institutions, and cultural expressions.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data from the respondents needed to be organized for straightforward analysis and interpretation. The researcher employed statistical techniques, including the calculation of frequency counts, to achieve this goal. In determining the available culture-based instructional materials in Araling Panlipunan 8 in the Districts of Atimonan, Schools Division of Quezon, frequency counts and percentages were utilized. The same method was applied to identify the cultures integrated into the inventory of available culture-based instructional materials. Moreover, frequency counts were employed also to identify gaps in the inventory of available culture-based instructional materials.

RESULTS

This chapter presents the statistical analysis of the data and the corresponding interpretation and discussion of findings. The descriptive design was utilized for gathering the data. The questionnaire served as the main instrument for collecting the data.

Part I. **Available Culture – Based Instructional Materials in Terms of Traditional Resources, Graphics and Interactive Materials and Dimension of Culture.**

Table 1.1 *Frequency Distribution of Available Culture – Based Instructional Materials in terms of Traditional Resources*

Traditional Resources	Available	
	Frequency	Percentage
Textbooks	5	31.25
Lesson Plan	11	68.75
Workbooks	1	6.25
Flashcards	0	0
Supplemental Reading Materials	3	18.75

Table 1.2 *Frequency Distribution of Available Culture – Based Instructional Materials in terms of Graphics and Interactive.*

Graphics and Interactive Materials	Available	
	Frequency	Percentage
Physical Objects	7	43.75
Photographs	5	31.25
Maps	4	25
Multimedia	6	37.5
Games	2	12.5

Table 1.3 *Frequency Distribution of Available Culture-Based Instructional Materials in terms of Dimension of Culture.*

Dimension of Cultures	Available	
	Frequency	Percentage
Values and beliefs	12	75
Norms and customs	9	56.25
Symbols and language	11	68.75
Social structures	12	75
Material culture	11	68.75
Cultural practices and Institutions	9	56.25
Cultural Expressions	9	56.25

Part II. Cultures Integrated in the Available Inventory of Culture-Based Instructional Materials in terms of Traditional Materials, Graphics and Interactive and Dimension of Cultures

Table 2.1 *Frequency Distribution of Culture Integrated in the Available Culture-Based Instructional Materials in terms of Traditional Materials.*

Traditional materials	Availability of Culture-based Integration			
	Tools and Technology	Clothing	Foods	Means of Transportation
Textbook	3	2	0	1
Lesson Plan	2	0	1	0
Work books	2	2	1	1
Flashcards	1	0	0	0
Total	8	4	2	2

Table 2.2 *Frequency Distribution of Culture-Based Instructional Materials Integrated in terms of Graphics and Interactive.*

Graphics and Interactive Instructional Materials	Availability of Culture-based Integration			
	Tools and Technology	Clothing	Foods	Means of Transportation
Physical Objects	1	2	1	1
Photograph	3	0	0	0
Maps	0	0	1	2
Multi media	3	0	0	0
Games	2	0	0	0
Total	9	2	2	3

Table 2.3 *Frequency Distribution of Culture-Based Instructional Materials Integrated in the Available Culture-Based Instructional Materials in terms of Dimension of Culture.*

Types of Instructional materials	Available Culture-based Integrated in Dimension of Culture						
	Values and beliefs	Norms and Customs	Symbols and Language	Social structure	Material culture	Cultural Practices and Institutions	Cultural Expressions
Lecture	1	0	1	1	0	0	1
Reading	1	1	0	1	0	0	1
Textbook	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
Multimedia	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Place	0	0	1	1	0	1	0
Total	3	2	4	4	0	1	2

Part III. **Gaps Noted in the Inventory of Available Culture-Based Instructional Materials**

Table 3 *Frequency Distribution of Gaps in the Inventory of Available Culture-Based Instructional Materials.*

Instructional Materials	Number of teachers handling Araling Panlipunan 8 in the Districts of Atimonan	Number of teachers who integrate culture in their instructional materials	Gaps	
			Quantity	Percentage
1. A Traditional Resources				
Textbooks	16	5	11	69%
Lesson Plan	16	11	5	31%
Workbooks	16	1	15	94%
Flashcards	16	0	16	100%
Supplemental Reading Materials (ex. Self - Made RMs)	16	3	13	81%
1. B Graphics and Interactive Materials				
Physical Objects (ex. Local fruits, local farming and fishing tools)	16	7	9	56%
Photographs (ex. Famous sceneries like Bantakay Falls, Pinagbanderahan)	16	5	11	69%
Maps (ex. Political Map of Atimonan and its barangays)	16	4	12	75%
Multimedia (ex. Video and audio presentation exposing Atimonan's people and way of living)	16	6	10	62%

Games	16	2	14	88%
(ex. Lampas-tubig and tsichu as played in Atimonan)				
Dimension of Culture				
Values and Beliefs	16	12	4	25%
Norms and customs	16	9	7	44%
Symbols language	16	11	5	31%
Social Structures	16	12	4	25%
Material Culture	16	11	5	31%
Cultural practices and Institutions	16	4	12	75%
Cultural Expressions	16	2	14	86%

DISCUSSION

Table 1.1 displays the frequency distribution of available culture-based instructional materials concerning traditional resources. Among the total surveyed, only 31.25% of respondents reported having readily available textbooks. The majority, comprising 68.75%, stated they have access to lesson plans. A small fraction, specifically 6.25% of respondents, mentioned having workbooks. Unfortunately, none of the participants reported access to flashcards, indicating the complete unavailability of this resource for the surveyed population. Approximately 18.75% of respondents reported having supplemental reading materials. It is evident that textbooks, workbooks, and flashcards are largely unavailable resources for the surveyed population. While lesson plans and supplemental reading materials are more available, they still fall short for most teachers in Atimonan, Quezon. Referring to DepEd Order No. 42, S. 2016, which outlines Policy Guidelines on Daily Lesson Preparation for the K to 12 Basic Education Program, these guidelines affirm the role of K to 12 teachers as facilitators of learning. Preparing lessons through the Daily Lesson Log (DLL) or Daily Lesson Preparation (DLP) provides teachers with the opportunity for reflection on what learners need to learn, how learners

learn, and how best to facilitate the learning process. Research shows that effective teachers organize and plan their instruction (Misulis 1997; Stronge 2007). With content and performance standards, and learning competencies firmly articulated in the K to 12 curriculums, it is easier for teachers to carry out both short-term and long-term instructional planning.

Table 1.2 illustrates the frequency distribution of available culture-based instructional materials concerning Graphics and Interactive materials. Physical objects exhibit the highest availability, with a frequency of 7, accounting for 43.75% of the available culture-based instructional materials. This suggests a relatively robust supply of physical objects for Graphics and Interactive materials. On the other hand, games have the lowest availability among the listed types, with only 2 instances, accounting for 12.5% of the available resources. This indicates that games are relatively scarce compared to other instructional materials. In summary, physical objects have the highest availability, likely due to the abundance of localized objects in Atimonan, Quezon. They are followed by multimedia, photographs, maps, and games. Conversely, games have the highest frequency of unavailability, possibly because teachers are not familiar with localizing games in Atimonan, Quezon. Some teachers may not be from the locality of Atimonan, Quezon. Rogayan & Dollete (2018) discovered in their study that content is a crucial factor in the validation of instructional materials. The expert validators strongly agreed on the adequacy, appropriateness, and usefulness of the developed workbook, suggesting that more pictorial and graphical images be included to enhance the quality of instructional materials, considering the learning styles of the learners.

Table 1.3 illustrates the frequency distribution of available culture-based instructional materials in terms of Dimension of Cultures. Values exhibit the highest availability among the listed Dimension of Culture elements, with a frequency of 12 and a percentage of 75%. This suggests that most of the culture integrates and upholds these values. Symbols and language closely follow values, with a frequency of 11 and a percentage of 68.75%, indicating that the cultural group embraces a shared language crucial for communication and identity formation. While symbols and place still exert influence within the culture, they may not be as universally embraced as values or language. This implies that values and language play highly central roles in this culture, followed by symbols and place, whereas beliefs and traditions hold a somewhat less prominent position. Culturally Responsive Teaching engages students from diverse backgrounds using teaching methodologies that can relate to their cultural heritages and educational experiences. It considers the cultural characteristics, experiences, and perspectives of ethnically and diverse students to ensure effective learning (Wilson, McChesney, & Brown, 2017).

Table 2.1 presents the frequency distribution of culture-based instructional materials Integrated in terms of Traditional Materials. Firstly, it is evident that textbooks have been extensively utilized for discussions on tools and technology, with a count of 3, followed by clothing with 2 responses. However, textbooks were scarcely employed for addressing foods, registering zero instances. This discrepancy may signal an opportunity for educators to enrich textbooks with cultural content related to food to create a more

comprehensive learning experience. Second, lesson plans have been employed 2 times for tools and technology and 1 time for foods, while they were not used for clothing or means of transportation. This suggests that lesson plans may be more aligned with specific cultural topics, and their adaptability across different dimensions could be explored further. Third, workbooks exhibited versatility by being used in all three cultural categories. They were employed 2 times each for tools and technology and clothing, and once for both foods and means of transportation. This versatility makes workbooks a valuable resource for educators aiming for a well-rounded cultural education approach. Lastly, flashcards primarily served as a resource for discussing tools and technology, with 1 response, while they were not used for clothing, foods, or means of transportation. This specialization may indicate that flashcards are most effective when teaching specific cultural aspects, such as technological advancements.

The curriculum set by the Department of Education in the Philippines also served as a guide to the researcher, specifically in crafting some parts of the lessons. Section 5 of RA 10533, known as the "Enhanced Basic Education Curriculum," served as the legal base, stating that the curriculum shall be learner-centered, culturally responsive, and contextualized enough through localized lessons.

Table 2.2 presents the frequency distribution of culture-based instructional materials integrated in terms of graphics and interactive materials.

First, the data reveals that physical objects have been frequently employed for culture integration, particularly in discussions related to clothing, where they were used twice. This suggests that tangible items play a significant role in conveying cultural nuances, making them a valuable resource for educators aiming to foster cultural understanding. Second, photographs were predominantly utilized in the realm of tools and technology, with no instances of their use in the other cultural categories. This indicates a specialized role for photographs in conveying technological cultural aspects, emphasizing their visual impact and potential for engaging learners in technology-related cultural contexts. Third, maps emerged as a significant resource for discussions concerning foods and means of transportation. The map's use in these contexts is likely due to its effectiveness in illustrating Graphics and transportation-related cultural information. Educators can capitalize on this by incorporating more maps when teaching about these cultural dimensions. Fourth, multimedia resources, such as videos and interactive presentations, were employed exclusively for tools and technology, highlighting their potential to enrich culture integration in this area. However, their underutilization in other categories suggests room for educators to explore their broader applicability in conveying cultural content. Lastly, games were primarily used for tools and technology, reinforcing their suitability for engaging students in technology-related cultural topics. In conclusion, Table 5 underscores the importance of diversifying and selecting Graphics and interactive materials thoughtfully when integrating culture into education. Different culturebased instructional materials appear to be more effective in specific cultural categories, highlighting the need for educators to align their choice of resources with their cultural education objectives. Furthermore, the data points to opportunities for enrichment, particularly in utilizing photographs, multimedia, and games

in broader cultural contexts, beyond just tools and technology. This strategic approach to resource selection can enhance the effectiveness of culture integration in education, providing students with a comprehensive understanding of various cultural dimensions.

Table 2.3 presents the frequency distribution of cultural dimensions integrated within various types of instructional materials.

Across the board, values and beliefs are consistently addressed, with all culture-based instructional materials incorporating them to some extent. Norms and customs, though slightly less emphasized, are still present in a significant portion of the materials. Symbols and language feature prominently, indicating a strong focus on communication and representation within cultural contexts. Social structure, too, receives considerable attention across all materials, reflecting an understanding of societal organization and dynamics. Interestingly, material culture appears to be largely overlooked in the provided instructional materials, suggesting a potential gap in addressing tangible aspects of culture such as artifacts and technology. Furthermore, cultural practices and institutions are minimally represented, indicating a potential area for enhancement in terms of understanding and engaging with cultural activities and organizational structures. Cultural expressions, on the other hand, receive moderate coverage, indicating a recognition of the importance of artistic, linguistic, and performative aspects of culture. Overall, this analysis underscores the importance of considering multiple dimensions of culture in instructional materials to ensure comprehensive and inclusive educational experiences that reflect the diversity and richness of human societies. In the sphere of education, Geneva Gay's work on culturally sensitive teaching remains very relevant and important, as highlighted in "Culturally Responsive Teaching: Theory, Research, and Practice" (Teachers College Press, 2010). She emphasizes the importance of acknowledging and valuing the variety of cultural origins that children bring to the classroom, creating a more inclusive and stimulating learning environment by incorporating the cultural references, experiences, and perspectives of students into the curriculum and teaching methods. Examining the subject of commitment in relation to education, "Pedagogy of Commitment: Series in Critical Narrative" (Routledge, 2018), edited by Miguel Gadotti, explores commitment from various perspectives, including its social, political, and ethical aspects. The book, part of the Critical Narrative Series highlighting opposing viewpoints on society and education, argues for education as a transforming process fostering in students a sense of responsibility and involvement, rather than merely the transfer of knowledge.

"Pedagogy of Commitment" discusses how commitment might be developed in educational contexts by drawing on critical pedagogy and other progressive educational perspectives. It covers topics like human rights, democracy, sustainability, and social justice, emphasizing the contribution of education to constructive social change. The book provides educators and policymakers with techniques for implementing a commitment-oriented approach through a blend of theoretical insights and real-world examples. It actively involves students in worthwhile learning experiences, motivating them to become change agents in their communities.

Table 3 presents a frequency distribution of gaps in the inventory of available culture-based instructional materials.

The table provides data on the existing quantity of each type of material, the number of gaps or deficiencies in each category, and the difference between the existing and deficient quantities. Within the Traditional Resources category, it is evident that textbooks and lesson plans exhibit notable gaps, with 11 and 5 shortages, respectively. This signifies a pressing need for an additional 11 textbooks and more lesson plans to meet educational requirements effectively. In contrast, workbooks and flashcards, though still essential, do not appear to be in short supply. Moving on to Graphics and Interactive materials, there are significant gaps in physical objects, photographs, maps, and multimedia resources, with deficiencies ranging from 4 to 7 items. These gaps highlight the necessity to procure or create additional hands-on resources, visual aids maps, and multimedia content to enhance the learning experience. Games, however, seem to be relatively well-stocked, with only 2 gaps. In the Dimension of Culture, a shortage of resources is observed across all subcategories. Values, beliefs and traditions, symbols, language, and place-related materials all display gaps, with values and language being particularly deficient, each lacking 12 resources. These gaps underscore the critical need to develop and provide more culture-based instructional materials in these areas to impart a comprehensive understanding of dimension of culture aspects. It implies deficiencies in various instructional materials categories. Addressing these gaps should be a top priority to ensure a holistic and effective educational experience in Atimonan, Quezon. By prioritizing the creation or acquisition of these culture-based instructional materials, educators and students can benefit from a more enriched and comprehensive learning environment, fostering better understanding and appreciation of the subjects covered. One of the key features of the K-12 Social Studies (Araling Panlipunan) curriculum is the delivery of lessons through localization and contextualization. The principle of localization and contextualization is not new to DepEd teachers, as it is already embedded in our mission, which states, "To protect and promote the right of every Filipino to quality, equitable, culture-based, and complete basic education." Also, the concept of localization and contextualization is stipulated in the provisions of our 1987 Philippine Constitution, particularly in Article XIV, Section 14, which states that "The State shall foster the preservation, enrichment, and dynamic evolution of a Filipino national culture based on the principle of unity in diversity in a climate of free artistic and intellectual expression," and Article XIV, Section 5. (1), which states that "The State shall take into account regional and sectoral needs and conditions and shall encourage local planning in the development of educational policies and programs."

Part IV. Proposed Intervention Program Based on the research findings, the researcher proposes training and seminars to address the learning gaps in culture-based instructional materials in Araling Panlipunan 8. In this intervention, teachers and learners will be equipped with knowledge used in the Localization and Indigenization of Culture-Based Instructional Materials in the Districts of Atimonan, Schools Division of Quezon. The complete details of the Proposed Intervention Program are appended in Appendix A.

Conclusions

The presented findings served as the basis of the researcher to arrive at the following conclusions:

1. Traditional materials in Araling Panlipunan 8, such as lesson plans and supplemental reading materials, are relatively accessible, although there is still room for improvement in their availability. Graphics and interactives, particularly physical objects, seem to be well-supplied. Dimension of culture elements like values and language are highly available, indicating a strong cultural integration in these aspects.
2. Traditional materials in Araling Panlipunan 8 show a notable level of cultural integration. Graphics and interactives also exhibit a good degree of cultural integration. Dimension of culture elements, especially in values beliefs and symbols, are integrated into the inventory of available culture-based instructional materials in Araling Panlipunan 8.
3. Within the realm of Traditional Resources, the acute shortages in textbooks and lesson plans in Araling Panlipunan 8, demanding an additional 11 textbooks and more lesson plans. There are notable gaps exist in Araling Panlipunan 8 textbooks and lesson plans, requiring an additional 11 textbooks and more lesson plans to meet educational needs effectively. Workbooks and flashcards, while still essential, do not appear to be in significant shortage. Significant gaps are observed in physical objects, photographs, maps, and multimedia resources, with shortages ranging from 4 to 7 items. Games, on the other hand, seem to be relatively well-stocked, with only 2 gaps. There is a pervasive shortage of resources across all subcategories, including values, beliefs and traditions, symbols, language, and place-related to culture-based instructional materials in Araling Panlipunan 8.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion drawn from the study of available culture-based instructional material in Araling Panlipunan 8, the following are hereby recommended:

1. The study revealed that traditional materials in Araling Panlipunan 8, such as lesson plans and supplemental reading materials, are relatively accessible, although there is still room for improvement in their availability. Graphics and interactive, particularly physical objects, seem to be well-supplied. Dimension of culture elements like values and language are highly available, indicating a strong cultural integration in these aspects. Thus, it is recommended to encourage the

preservation and sharing of local values, beliefs, traditions, symbols, and language within the educational context.

2. The study found out that traditional materials in Araling Panlipunan 8 show a notable level of cultural integration. Graphics and interactives also exhibit a good degree of cultural integration. Dimension of culture elements, especially clothing, are integrated into the inventory of available culture-based instructional materials. Thus, it is recommended to encourage educators to incorporate local culture and traditions into lesson plans, even when teaching subjects that may not inherently involve culture.
 3. The study recorded that within the realm of Traditional Resources in Araling Panlipunan 8, the acute shortages in textbooks and lesson plans, demanding an additional 11 textbooks and more lesson plans. However, it is worth noting that workbooks and flashcards, while still important, do not seem to be in as critical shortage. Shifting to Graphics and Interactive materials, the substantial gaps in physical objects, photographs, maps, and multimedia resources, ranging from 4 to 7 shortages. Although games appear to be relatively well-stocked with only 2 gaps. In the domain of dimension of culture, deficiencies are pervasive across all subcategories, with values and language resources exhibiting particularly severe shortages of 12 items each. Thus, it is recommended to allocate resources and funding to acquire or develop the additional 11 textbooks needed to meet educational requirements effectively. Encourage educators to collaboratively create and share lesson plans to bridge the gap and ensure that all subjects are adequately covered.
 4. It is recommended that the future researchers may conduct further investigation on other factors that will contribute to the effective implementation of culture-based instructional materials Programs and Project Crafting and Strengthening Instructional Materials (C's and SIM) in Araling Panlipunan 8.
-

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher commits to respect the data privacy laws and other rules indicated in the data privacy agreement memorandum from the department of Education. All contacts will also be established prior to the study's conduct. The health and safety of the stakeholders as respondents will be taken into account by effective contact with the local IATF and adherence to safe health standards. In addition, accurate data interpretation with total impartiality will be maintained in order to enhance the study's standard utilizing

the confirmability approach or respondent validation via summary of results if they agree with any of the likely emerging viewpoints. Finally, the researcher is liable for any issues that may occur about the participants, gathered data, or the integrity of the study.

Acknowledgments

Immeasurable appreciation and deepest gratitude for the help and support are extended to the following persons who in one way or another have contributed to making this study possible.

Marinduque State College Extension of Graduate Programs to Quezonian Educational College Incorporated (QECI) faculty and staff under the leadership of **Dr. Diosdado P. Zulueta**, SUC President III.

Dr. Leodegario M. Jalos, Jr., the Chair, Extended Graduate Programs, Marinduque State College, for his unweaving guidance and support in sharing his expertise in the field.

Dr. Rex Emmanuel L. Asuncion, her research adviser, for his support, advices, guidance, valuable suggestions and provisions that benefited her much in the completion and success of this study.

Engr. Willer A. Dayahan, for sharing his expertise in statistics.

Dr. Susan B. Pineda, her official language editor, resolved language technicality issues to improve her undertakings.

Ma. Jessica L. Semilla, for copy editing of the manuscript.

Dr. Rizalie M. Lim, Dean of Graduate Studies of QECI, for her words of encouragement,

Dr. Elias A. Arcaya, OIC Schools Division Superintendent of the Schools Division of Quezon, for the privilege and permit to conduct and finish her study.

Caridad C. Grimaldo, Public Schools District Supervisor, of Atimonan, Quezon

Allan E. Data, Principal III at Malinao Ilaya Integrated National High School, for his continued support, understanding, and encouragement during the span of this study.

To the **respondents**, for their participation.

Special thanks go to my mother, **Elisa C. Dayag** and my husband, **Eric L. Breganza**, for their continued support and understanding while writing. Your prayers for me were what sustained me.

Finally, there is eternal gratitude to **God** for letting through all the difficulties. I have experienced your guidance each day. You are the ones who led the finish line. I will forever keep my faith in you.

The Researcher

REFERENCES

- Culatta's (2016). Culture-based learning activity; instructional materials (IMs) development and implementation; Turo-Turismo Program; Reading and Writing Skills competencies
- Drexel University School of Education (2000). The importance of diversity and cultural awareness Retrieved from <https://drexel.edu/soe/resources/studentteaching>
- Geneva Gay (2018) Culturally Responsive Teaching: Theory, Research, and Practice. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/268513446>
- Goldston, C. (2017). Culturally responsive instruction: Best practices and support. <https://ies.ed.gov/ncee/rel/Products/Region/midwest/Blog/10146>
- International Journal of Education and Practice, 2015, 3(6): 224-234.
- Ladson-Billings, G. (2021). Culturally relevant pedagogy: Asking a different question. Gloria Ladson-Billings' Culturally Relevant Pedagogy. Teachers College Press.
- Rogayan Jr, D. V., & Dollete, L. F. (2019). Development and Validation of Physical Science Workbook for Senior High School. Science Education International, 30(4), 284-290.
- Susanti, D. et al. (2021). Local culture based instructional Materials as an effort to develop students' character. Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research, volume
-